

ECONOMIC CONDITIONS OF KASHMIR UNDER DUGRA PERIOD

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Abstract

The beauties of Kashmir have also been the causes of its outside intervention in course of her history. The Hindus, Mughals, Pathans, Sikhs, and finally Dogras have successively dominated this beautiful land. The culture of valley has drawn its strength and sustenance from various sources, influencing and getting influenced by these forces at work. The basic rights of the Kashmiri Muslims were trampled and the economic conditions of people were depressing. In levying and collecting the tax from the citizen's, the state functioned partially and communally all the classes of the Muslim community were tax payers except the tailors, the lake dwellers and even the poorest of all and worst of all paid taxes obviously because the dogra rulers always consider Jammu as their home land and Kashmir as the conquered territory.

Key words

Dogra, Hindu, Nanakshai, Pathans, Shawl, Sikhs, Treaty.

Introduction

The beauties of Kashmir has a long history intermittently ruled by outsiders and it is mainly divided into three periods; the early period is ruled by Hindus and Buddhist kings, Medieval period is ruled by Muslims and Sikhs and finally the Modern period is ruled by Dogra rulers and they have successively subjugated this beautiful land. Before the dogra rule the period of Afghans is regarded as the dark period in Kashmir history because of its cruel nature as there was loot and plunder in the state after Afghans, the Sikhs who were also the outsiders extracted much from the state as this was not their homeland. After the end of medieval period Kashmir came in to the hands of dogra rulers by the famous treaty of Amritsar signed on 16 March 1846 A.D. between Gulab Singh and British and is also known as sale deed of Kashmir. In consideration of this transfer Mehraja was to pay 75 lakhs of rupees (Nanakshai) and to present annually to the British govt. one horse, 12 perfect shawl goat of approved breed and 3 pairs of Kashmir shawls. The entire valley was commoditized and sold like property. It was therefore viewed more as an economic commodity than as a political possession. The British-Mehraja deal, the people's interest was not at all taken into consideration. Chris pother Thomas says, the people never asked for it, never wanted it and never loved it. The famous Urdu poet, Hafiz jallendhuri lamenting the treaty in following words:

The fate of Human beings was sold for Rs seventy five lakhs,

Kashmir's paradise was sold for Rs 75 lakhs.

And also Allama Iqbal lamenting upon the sale of Kashmir in following words,

Their fields, their crops, their streams;

Even the peasants in the vale, they sold,

They sold, all alas,

How cheap was the sale.

The dogra rule was forcefully enforced on the people valley, which were not given any choice by the British in the matter and were thus subjected to the world's most inhuman, torturous and miserable slavery. Robert thorp mentions, "the British deliberately sold millions of human beings into absolute power of one of the meanest, most avaricious, cruel and unprincipled ministers, courtiers, hangers on of every grade ho descended upon Kashmir like a flock of hungry vultures and swept away the prosperity and happiness of its people, for a fully selfish reason". So at the commencement of the dogra rule the economic condition of the valley was deplorable. At that time, Baron Schonberg, who travelled the Kashmir, observed, "I have not been more saddened by the conditions of human beings in many countries than in Kashmir". The abysmal mass poverty, misery,

hunger, disease and ignorance represented the extreme backwardness of the state, sweeping away the wealth and happiness of its people and having gone through a time of extreme exploitation at the hands of the dogra rulers, who were theoretically autonomous but in reality the stroges of the British imperialism, in general, the population of the state and that of the valley, in particular was living in the most miserable conditions. The peasants of Kashmir had no land ownership rights for the first time in history, while the Jammu peasants enjoyed full land ownership rights. In levying and collecting the tax from the citizen's, the state functioned partially and communally all the classes of the Muslim community were tax payers except the tailors, the lake dwellers and even the poorest of all and worst of all paid taxes. The dogra regime has spread its persecution to all shades of the Muslim population even the women and children also became victims of it. Exploitation had gone so deep and wide that women resorted to certain socially disapproved ill practices for the survival of their families. Robert thorp observes, the govt. protected and promoted this heinous crime, for giving permission to buy a girl for prostitution for about one hundred chilke rupees revenue to the government like the shawl bafs, these unfortunate women were legally forbidden from returning to normal lives. The selling of the young girls and in some cases children, did take place due to the grasping and avaricious nature of dogra govt. throp writes "the selling of young girls to known houses of ill-fame in kashmir is both protected an encouraged by the govt. and it helps to increase the portion of his revenue which the mehraja derives from the wages of prostitution". E. F. Knight says that any traveller visiting Kashmir can see for himself that the dogra officials in all parts of the country destroy the goose that lays the golden eggs for him". Begar's institution was a strong instrument of oppression and exploitation in the hands of corrupt government officials. In 1860's the economic conditions of Kashmir Young husband says about it, agriculture was declining in the early sixties, the people were miserably poor and in any other country their state would have been almost of starvation and famine.

In Kashmir valley majority of the people were Muslims and they were treated as second class citizens by government and his officials who were fiercely Hindu. Hindus were promoted and favoured in every way above the Muslims, they were usually exempt the system of begar and Hindu tax collectors were blatantly corrupt. However, in 1877-78 A.D. a deliberate policy of ethnic cleansing or genocide by starvation occurred with the death of thousands of Muslims in Kashmir, when the stock piles of food grain an additional supplies were seized by the Hindu govt. the year 1877 was cruel time. A bad season as added to excessive taxation, so that the people preferred leaving their crops to rot in the ground to gathering what would bring in so little profit to themselves. Villages were deserted, trade went down and starvation decreased the population. It was only with the last mehraja that a turning loomed in the long lane of Kashmir's misfortunes. The lolab valley was depopulated and a large extent of the district beyond that became deserts.

Through a different form of taxation system in Kashmir, shawl weavers who were wealthy during the Mughal period were poor by the 1870,s Young husband records on the manufacture of shawls parallel restrictions were placed. The wool was taxed as it entered kashmir, the manufacture was taxed for every workmen he employed and at various stages of the process according to the value of the fabric and lastly the merchant was taxed, before he could export the goods, the enormous duty of 85% and valorem, butchers, carpenters, boatmen and even prostitutes were still taxed and coolies who were engaged to carry loads for travellers had to give up half their earnings. Finally under the influence of socialism, Sheikh Mohammad Abdullah advocated the abolition of landlordism and the distribution of land to the tilter. The legacy of such kind of regressive policy based on over taxation, discrimination and the apathy towards the development of social and economic overheads was that in 1947 A.D. when the dogra rule virtually came to an end.

Conclusion

Subsequently treaty of Amritsar notoriously known as sale deed of Kashmir was concluded between Maharaja Gulab Singh and British govt. on 16 March 1846 at Amritsar, by his infamous treaty of Amritsar, the British govt. sold for ever to Maharaja and thus the Kashmiri became a stranger in his own country. The rules and regulations of cast hampered social mobility, fostered social divisions and snapped the individual identity. Muslims were discriminated not only on economic front but also the rulers interfered with their religious liberties. In short the dogra rulers would eat into the hard toil of artisans especially the shawl weavers by imposing having heavy taxes

on their products.

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